

The Heinrich Nissen's templum as proposed in the Leo Frobenius' Voice of Africa

A.C. Sparavigna

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Polytechnic University of Turin

In 1913, "The voice of Africa" by Leo Frobenius has been published. It was an account of the travels of the German Inner African Exploration Expedition in the years 1910-1912, made under Frobenius' leadership. Frobenius carried out excavations at the ancient Yoruba city of Ife in Nigeria, theorizing that the Ife bronze and terracotta sculptures were relics from Atlantis. Here, we are not concerned with the Frobenius' Atlantic Africa theory. We want to stress the fact that Frobenius knew the theory by Heinrich Nissen of the Templum, published in 1869. He used the Nissen's templum as evidence of an Atlantic Africa connection with the Mediterranean world.

Torino, June 17, 2024

In 1913, "The voice of Africa", "an account of the travels of the German Inner African Exploration Expedition in the years 1910-1912" has been published. The author was Leo Frobenius. The book describes the Fourth German Inner Africa Research Expedition in Nigeria and Cameroon between 1910 and 1912, under the Frobenius' leadership. Frobenius carried out excavations at the ancient Yoruba city of Ife in Nigeria, theorizing that the Ife bronze and terracotta sculptures were relics from Atlantis. About the discovery of a statue, he wrote: "Before us stood a head of marvellous beauty, wonderfully cast in antique bronze, true to the life, incrustated with a patina of glorious dark green. This was, in very deed, the Olokun, Atlantic Africa's Poseidon! Profoundly stirred, I stood for many minutes before this remnant of the erstwhile Lord and Ruler of the Empire of Atlantis". On Yoruba mythology, besides Frobenius, see Apter, 2022.

Here, we are not concerned with the Frobenius' Atlantic Africa theory. We want to stress the fact that Frobenius knew the theory by Heinrich Nissen of the Templum, published in 1869. He used the Nissen's templum as evidence of an Atlantic Africa connection with the Mediterranean world.

As we did in many previous discussions, we are here remarking once more that the Nissen's belief of the templum arrived almost unrecognized, in particular in today archaeoastronomy of the Roman world. In fact, to my best knowledge, I was the first to stress the Nissen's theory about the direction of the decumanus determined according to the sunrise. Nissen proposed to compare the azimuths of sunrise and decumanus to determine the Dies Natalis of the town. The Nissen theory was well-known in the past (Nietzsche, 1878, Posani Löwenstein, 2012, Cassirer, 1923, 1929) and was also criticized by many scholars (as shown by Sparavigna, 2020-2024, Nissen was criticized by Castagnoli, 1971, 1984, Catalano, 1978, De Petra, 1869, Erdmann, 1883, Le Gall, 1972, Thulin, 1905, Valetton, 1892, 1893, 1898). Recently, in 2007, archaeoastronomer G. Magli proposed a similar theory without mentioning Heinrich Nissen. So, we have some archaeoastronomy claiming being able to find the Dies Natalis of the Roman towns using the direction of the sunrise. We have cases where the Dies Natalis is known, but the direction of the sunrise does not coincide with the direction of the sunrise along the decumanus (see [The Dies Natalis of Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium and of Augusta Treverorum](#)).

Travelled by sea

Returning to Frobenius, in Kalous, 1970, we can find told that the main argument is about "the historical possibilities of trading and cultural contacts by sea between the Guinean Coast and the Old Mediterranean".

For instance, we need to locate the port of Tartessos, that “we can suppose that it already existed in the second millennium B. C. and imported tin from England in exchange for Spanish silver and copper”. “Frobenius claimed that Tartessos was a port of the Sea Peoples Tursha mentioned in Egyptian sources of the twelfth century B. C. and that the Sea Peoples were the ancestors of the Etruscans”. “Some connection between the Tursha and Tarshish is quite possible; a historical relationship between the Sea Peoples and the Etruscans seems to be beyond doubt” (Kalous, 1970, about Tarshish and Tartessos, see López-Ruiz, 2009). However, “There is no written evidence that the Sea Peoples travelled by sea as far as the Guinean Coast. But there is some evidence that these trips were possible in the first millennium B. C. According to Strabo, 'There were ancient settlements of Tyrians, now deserted - no fewer than three hundred cities, which were destroyed by the Pharusians and the Nigritae; and these people . . . are at a distance of a thirty days' journey from Lynx' . A trip to the West African coast by Euthymenes could have taken place in about 600 B. C. He saw crocodiles ...” (see more in Kalous, 1970). “All these written records can be considered evidence that expeditions by sea on the coast of West Africa were possible in the first millennium B. C. and that some probably took place. ... Fraser has suggested that the Mediterranean influences on West Africa were of just this unspecific, "international" kind and Pallotino has suggested that the Etruscan culture was not a distinct one but a local variation of this "international" Mediterranean culture. Frobenius presented a "list" (not a very systematic one and one which varied considerably in his different books) of cultural features in the Atlantic area which he claimed had been derived from the Old Mediterranean” (Kalous, 1970).

Kalous discusses these features. “Firstly, we have the Impluvium type of building. There is no doubt that this architectural form existed in the Old Mediterranean and that it was the Etruscans (or their Sea Peoples ancestors) who had started it there - and that basically the same form existed on the Guinean Coast, in Benin, Iboland, Ife, the Cameroons, the Gold Coast and Togo. According to Foyle, 'so striking is the resemblance to Roman examples that theories have been advanced linking the Benin plans with Roman sources via Egypt. ... Wölfel stated that there were house-urns in Italy which remind us of Yoruba houses. Of course, this does not prove that there were contacts between the Etruscans and the peoples of what is now Southern Nigeria, but the existence of impluvium there (and elsewhere in West Africa) is certainly not easy to explain in terms of a quite independent origin” (Kalous, 1970, and references therein).

“Another item is the so called Templum concept in which the world is regarded as having four sides, North, South, East, West and four imaginary main "points" midway along each side. The line connecting East and West was called Decumanus by the Romans, the one connecting North and South Carado. Both names and the whole system were taken over by the Romans from the Etruscans who had further divided each of the main sides of the World into a further 4 making 16 in all. More or less the same idea with the dominant numbers of 4 and 16 exists among the Yoruba and the Bini; and seems to be reflected in the four-day week of the peoples of the Guinean Coast. The territory where the four-day week is found is roughly that of Frobenius' Atlantic culture. Also the whole of the so-called Ifa divination with its prominent number of 16 seems to be relevant. There are several theories about its origin. Tegnaeus claimed that Ifa was 'sans doute d'une origine paleo-mediterrannee'. Frobenius collected at Ife some legends to the effect that it was a gift by the god Eshu to mankind. The number 16 appears again and again” (Kalous, 1970). Kalous reports that “Four and sixteen, and also the square of sixteen, 256, are given especial significance in Ifa ... In Ifa symbolism, the world picture shows four cardinal points each governed by an orisa; the Yoruba town has conceptually four gates; and the masked messenger of the ancestors is four-headed”.

“Whenever the god Eshu wants to make the people quarrelsome, he walks on the main line (East- West) in the opposite direction (West-East). He is wearing a four-colour cap whose front is green, back black, left side red and right side white. It may be evidence in support of Frobenius' theory that the same colour symbolism (and even the same order of colours) existed in the Old Mediterranean - although yellow there replaced green. The Greek philosopher Heraclitus from Ephesus (530-470 B. C.) considered black, white, yellow and red - in that order - the fundamental colours. ... The same colours - but not arranged in the same order - existed in the Maya culture: East was associated with red, North with white, West with black and South with yellow” (Kalous, 1970, and references therein). Let us also add the mythological creatures of Chinese culture, which

are the guardians of the four cardinal directions. They are the Azure Dragon of the East, the Vermilion Bird of the South, the White Tiger of the West, and the Black Tortoise of the North.

“Frobenius was quite aware of the spread of the Templum concept in Asia and America; in Africa however he considered it isolated and explained it as a foreign import” (Kalous, 1970). Let us stress that ‘templum’ in Rome does not mean “temple”, that is the dwelling place of a divinity. The templum is a special place where the Roman àugurs asked for Iuppiter’s approval. Please consider this fact in reading the following Frobenius’ words. Please consider the discussion in Catalano, 1978, “Aspetti spaziali del sistema giuridico-religioso romano. Mundus, templum, urbs, ager, Latium, Italia”, and also [“The Town and the Templum, in the Discussions by Nissen, Nietzsche, Valetton, Catalano and many others”](#).

Quid enim scire Etrusci haruspices aut de tabernaculo rede capto aut de pomerium iure potuerunt? [Cicero, De div., 2, 35, 75:]. What could the Etruscan soothsayers know about the right way to erect the tent (tabernacle) or the laws of the pomerium? The templum is a specific entity in Rome, and it is not managed by Etruscan soothsayers.

Frobenius’ words in the Voice of Africa

“A savant, named Heinrich Nissen [in the English text, the name is given as Rissen], published a book with this title, “The Templum,” in 1869. In this, one of the most valuable contributions of last century to the history of civilization, its author expounded the method in which in ancient times the foundational plan of old Italian towns, military encampments, temples, and also domestic dwellings was conditioned by the lay of the land. A road was built running from east to west called Via Decumana. It started from a highway running north and south, called Via Cardua. Not only was the organization of settlements dependent on these four directions, but the site of places of worship was arranged in accordance with them. The Romans had four, but the Etruscans, from whom the Romans adopted the basic idea of the system, had sixteen of these directions. On these lines, then, every such ground-plan expressed the Templum, i.e., if we translate the meaning of this word freely, the ancient philosophic idea of the universe” (Frobenius).

"Die Limitation [centuriation] geht aus von den Weltgegenden: eine Linie von Ost nach West und eine zweite, welche jene rechtwinklig schneidet, von Süd nach Nord bilden die Basis del ganzen Systems. Frontin p. 27 (nach ihm Hygin p. 166, Dolabella p. 303)"(Nissen, 1869). In fact, the limitation, that is the land surveying practice of the Roman, is mirroring the division of the world in four parts; it is based on two lines, one east west, the other south.north, This is the basis of the system.

“It was the physical expression of the belief that it was divided into four or, respectively, sixteen parts, of which each four were assumed to be subject to a divine control. Now, the antique Etruscans who are known to have been extremely credulous, arranged the whole of their lives from the points of view dictated to them by soothsayers. And they, moreover, had, inter alia , a species of oracle, in which the future and the will of the gods could be divined in the course taken by flashes of lightning. They cut up the entire horizon, or the world of sight, into sixteen parts, and from the section in which flashes were seen to go and, from the way they followed each other, the future and the will of the Gods were foretold. It was the Tyrrhenians who, in the course of their migrations, brought the fundamental idea of this image of the universe out of Asia Minor into Etruria. Von Hommel and Milani’s researches have proved that these imaginations of the All were at the root of the religious cult and forms of worship of erstwhile Babylonia, Tiryms (or Troy) and Etruria. If, now, we compare the true inwardness of the Etruscan religion, which is perhaps best preserved in the antiquities of Etrurian posterity, with that of Yoruban belief, we shall at once see that the Via Decumana corresponds with the “Chief Way” of the Yorubans, and that the Via Cardua corresponds with the “ Second Way ” of our Atlantic nations. And we shall furthermore see that the sixteen interpretations of the lightning-oracle are essentially the same as the sixteen Odus. Sixteen gods dwell in sixteen celestial habitations in Etruria as well as Yoruba” (Frobenius).

It is better to stress that Roman àugurs managed the templum, not the Etruscans soothsayers.

“This coincidence can be followed in its subtlest ramifications. All the believers in the ancient image of the universe, in the idea of the Templum, had, like the Yorubans, a week of five days, which was only afterwards, apparently owing to the prevalence of South Semitic elements, extended to an hebdomadal week. I should like, yet briefly, to point out that in those very remote old days there must have been nations endowed with memories of this Templum ideal, such, for example, as the Indo-Germanic peoples of the North, whose relations to centres of Asiatic culture it is difficult to prove otherwise. They, too, originally had a five-day week, and special Gods presided over the destinies of the days specially sacred to them. Three such deities at least can be shown to be most strikingly identical with some of the Yoruban gods. Shango corresponds to the once most mighty Donar. Obatalla corresponds to Wotan, the Lord of Heaven, whose “countenance was turned towards the south.” And our Ogun is the exact counterpart of the Battle-God. These divinities of the sword in the North are honoured among many Germanic tribes with symbols exactly similar to those of the Yorubans, as well as amongst the Scythians, and in the South in the form of Mars, the mighty sire of great Romulus. Attention must, however, be called to one slight difference, important perhaps on account of the digression involved. When the ancient Romans prayed, they turned, in following the course of the sun from East to West southwards ; that is to say, they turned round to the right. Pliny makes this very pertinent observation : “When we (Romans) pray, we bring our right hands to our mouths and turn our whole bodies round (to the right), while the Gauls turn to the left.” Now what is very remarkable, indeed, is that the custom of turning in a given direction to pray, which prevails amongst the Yorubans, should not only be precisely the same as that adopted in the mental attitude of the Romans and the Gauls, but especially that they turn to the left, which is the custom peculiar to the Gauls” (Frobenius).

“Taking it all in all then, we observe a persistent identity in the image of the world, in ritual and fundamental philosophy. We see that the religion of our Atlantic region must, beyond all doubt, be conceived as participation in a system of worship brought to the high state of perfection pertaining to a vast area of civilization, not only in its peculiarities, but in the complete and uniform originality of its essentials. This remarkable Yoruban religion is not unique. It is definitely linked to the perfected system of a primeval age. It is not incumbent upon me to compare the individual portions of an earlier civilization which permeated and dominated the world by its stimulating force and its results, or to bring the various stages of its development into connection. Recognition of the fact as such is the one essential, and we are able to point out problems and interrogations whose solution and responses will be equivalent to an enormous advancement of our knowledge of universal history. This is the purport of the Yoruban conception of the world I was enabled to unravel. I would like to give at least one more proof of this old-world philosophy’s extensive dissemination, and this ancient civilization’s power of expansion” (Frobenius)

Frobenius’ illustration at the end of the chapter.

“At this chapter’s close I append an illustration, where four different crosses are placed in juxtaposition. The first of these shows the picture of the world drawn by my Yoruban teacher in the sand. When he had finished, he said : “ The image could be presented just as well with two sticks, and their preparation would quite exactly portray the way of arriving at the Odu. And in this way: Wherever an Odu is marked with only a single stroke, a ring of the bark must be removed. Where there are two marks, it must remain. So a picture is formed of four pieces of stick, the right hand one of which is white and bare of bark, the left, however, still quite dark, because no bark has been removed. The two ends of the upper limb of the cross are barked, and also the middle portion of the lower limb.” The reader can see for himself that this picture does, in fact, correspond with the Odu presented by the Ifa tray’s medium. I designed the third image from the method of divination with four dice practised by the Pueblo-Indians of Arizona, in America. It is precisely the same in the direction of the four cardinal points, according to the myths and the cult observed by these tribes. I can spare myself further description. I have gone to another part on the other side of the world, namely, Korea, for the fourth illustration. The Koreans symbolize the four quarters of the heavens in strokes, just like the Yorubans. Thus we see that there the omission of the centre line represents absolute light in the East ; absolute darkness in the West is shown by the line along all the length of the limb ; the light in the South by the break in the centre of the line in the inferior, and the light in the North by the break in the centre line of the ends of the superior, limb” (Frobenius).

And we find mentioned again the Etruscans

“And, after that, we inquired into their methods of divination and the meaning of their primitive myths, and were surprised here to find an exalted idea of the universe, in which the State and its clan-units, the past ages and the present times, the dead and the living were combined. It is a system whose equal in consistency of conception is only paralleled among the famous Etruscans of legendary Rome. The centre of this antique Templum, within whose frame the world of Gods, sixteen in number, is enclosed in habitations suited to their respective powers, finds crystallized expression in the ancient Holy City, the fastness of the Sea God, the Holy City from whose soil relics of classic beauty, specimens of an older form of art and proofs of long-lost craftsmanship can be extracted” (Frobenius).

“Located in southwestern Nigeria, the ancient city of Ife is considered by the Yoruba people to be the birthplace of humankind. Yoruba tradition holds that Ife (also called Ile-Ife) is a holy city that was established by the god Oduduwa as the capital of an influential kingdom” ([Britannica](#)).

A section of Frobenius’ work is discussing the “distribution of the Templum idea” .

“All that was possible with regard to the ideas of the universe entertained by the nations of Africa proper has been said. I have shown that the Atlantic Yoruban conception of the Temple signifies an organized imagination of the world and religion on a much larger scale. Not so much as a spark of clearness in this respect was I able to find amongst other African peoples. The Mandes and Bosses, it is true, very well remember that four gods or pairs of gods rule over the four seasons of the year and dwell in different parts of the heavens. But beyond this one legend and tradition they have lost all other knowledge. Therefore, the religion of the Atlantic nations is unique, and we should be forced beforehand to renounce every possibility of being able to trace any transcontinental relation, if there were nothing whatever left by which the continuance of investigation were assured” (Frobenius).

Frobenius continues discussing the sand oracle, where we find *“the symbolic four divisions according to the cardinal points of the heavens. ... [Frobenius] found exactly the same divination by sand in Algeria. ... Sand-divination is said to be unusual in the Sahara, and, if so, we should again see a proof of littoral distribution and lack of trans-continental relation. ... Summarizing the results, we obtain a uniform picture. Northern Africa shows elements of civilization similar to those of the Atlantic side. There is no forthcoming evidence of a continental connection. If such had ever existed, it must to-day be declared to have been completely wiped out” (Frobenius).*

References

1. Apter, A. (2022). Frobenius unbound: Black Atlantis and the poetics of displacement in the Yoruba diaspora. *Paideuma*, 68, 119-148.
2. Cassirer, E. (1955). *The philosophy of symbolic forms: Volume two: Mythical thought*. Yale University Press.
3. Cassirer, E. (1953). *The Philosophy of Symbolic Forms*. Translated by Ralph Manheim. Yale University Press.
4. Cassirer, E. (1923-29). *Philosophie der symbolischen Formen, Zweiter Teil: Das mythische Denken*.
5. Castagnoli, F. (1958). *Topografia e urbanistica di Roma*, Editore: L. Cappelli.
6. Castagnoli, F. (1959). *Centuriazione*, Enciclopedia dell'Arte Antica (1959). Treccani
7. Castagnoli, F. (1971). *Orthogonal town planning in antiquity*, Cambridge, Mass., MIT Press.
8. Castagnoli, F. (1984). *Il Tempio Romano: Questioni di Terminologia e di Tipologia*. Papers of the British School at Rome. Vol. 52 (1984), pp. 3-20 (18 pages)
9. Catalano, P. (1978). *Aspetti spaziali del sistema giuridico-religioso romano. Mundus, templum, urbs, ager, Latium, Italia*, in ANRW, *Principat, II, 16, 1*, a cura di H. Temporini e W. Haase, Berlin-New York, pp. 442-553.
10. Catalano, P., & Haase, W. (1978). *Aspetti spaziali del sistema giuridico-religioso romano. Mundus, templum, urbs, ager, Latium, Italia* (pp. 440-553). Walter De Gruyter.
11. Conventi, M. (2004). *Città romane di fondazione* (No. 130). L'Erma di Bretschneider.
12. De Petra, G. (1869). *Giornale degli Scavi di Pompei (nuova serie)*, Maggio-Giugno 1869, Recensione al libro di Heinrich Nissen intitolato *Das Templum. Antiquarische Untersuchungen Mit astronomischen Hülfsstafeln von B. Tiele*, 1869.
13. De Petra, G. (1869). *Recensione del Das Templum. Giornale degli Scavi di Pompei (nuova serie)*, Maggio-Giugno.
14. Eckstein, A. M. (1979). *The Foundation Day of Roman Coloniae*. *California Studies in Classical Antiquity*, 12, 85-97.
15. Erdmann, M. (1883). *Zur Kunde der hellenistischen Städtegründungen*, Strassburg.
16. Frobenius, L. (1913). *The Voice of Africa: being an account of the travels of the German Inner African Exploration Expedition in the years 1910-1912* (Vol. 1). Hutchinson & Company.
17. Frobenius, L., & Bovero, C. (1991). *Storia delle civiltà africane*. Bollati Boringhieri.
18. Kalous, M. (1970). *Leo Frobenius' Atlantic Theory-A Reconsideration*. *Paideuma*, 27-51.
19. Le Gall, J. (1972). *Les rites de fondation des villes romaines*. *Bulletin de la Société nationale des Antiquaires de France Année 1972* 1970 pp. 292-307 Electronic copy available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4700361>
20. Le Gall, J. (1975). *Les romains et l'orientation solaire*. *MEFRA* 87-1975-1, p. 287-320.
21. López-Ruiz, C. (2009). *Tarshish and Tartessos revisited: textual problems and historical implications*. In *Colonial Encounters in Ancient Iberia: Phoenician, Greek, and Indigenous Relations*. Edited by Michael Dietler, and Carolina Lopez-Ruiz (eds). University of Chicago Press, 2009. Chicago Scholarship Online, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226148489.003.0010>.
22. Magli, G. (2007). *On the orientation of Roman towns in Italy*. arXiv:physics/0703213 [physics.pop-ph]
23. Nietzsche, F. (1878). *Der Gottesdienst der Griechen, Alterthümer des religiösen Cultus der Griechen; Vorlesung Winter 1875/76 und Winter 1877/78*.
24. Nietzsche, F. (2016). *Il servizio divino dei greci* (Vol. 21). Adelphi Edizioni spa.
25. Nietzsche, F. (1900). *Gesammelte Werke, 1844-1900*, al sito archive.org (indirizzo web <https://archive.org/details/gesammeltewerke05nietuoft/page/354/mode/2up>).
26. Nissen, H. (1869). *Das Templum, antiquarische Untersuchungen, mit astronomische Hülfsstafeln von B. Tiele*. Weidmannsche Buchhandlung, Berlin.
27. Nissen, H. (1902). *Italische Landeskunde: Bd. Die Staedte*. 1902 (Vol. 2). Weidmannsche buchhandlung.

28. Nissen, H. (1906). *Orientation, studien zur geschichte der religion*. Weidmann, Berlin.
29. Nissen, H. (1906). *Orientation: Studien zur Geschichte der Religion (Vol. 1)*. Weidmann.
30. Posani Löwenstein, M. (2012). *Il servizio divino dei Greci*. Adelphi.
31. Sparavigna, A. C. (2020, November 8). *L'archeoastronomia e la Nissenschen Theorie, ovvero quanto disse Heinrich Nissen sull'orientazione solare del Templum*. Zenodo.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4439304>
32. Sparavigna, A. C. (2020, March 30). *La Limitatio Romana: Alcune Definizioni*. Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3733048
33. Sparavigna, A. C. (2020). *Brindisi e il suo giorno natale, tra cronologia ed astronomia*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4434668>
34. Sparavigna, A.C. (2020). *What the Latin Literature Truly Tells Us About the Orientation of Camps, Towns and Centuriation (August 6, 2020)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3675354> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3675354>
35. Sparavigna, A. C. (2021). *La recensione di Giulio De Petra al libro di Heinrich Nissen sul Templum*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5034544>
36. Sparavigna, A. C. (2021). *Friedrich Nietzsche e la direzione dei decumani delle città antiche (Friedrich Nietzsche and the Direction of the Decumani of Ancient Towns)*. Available at SSRN 3859474. First layout (2020), <https://zenodo.org/records/4171775>
37. Sparavigna, A. C. (2021, July 3). *Il Tempio Romano ed alcune questioni di terminologia come illustrati da Ferdinando Castagnoli (1984)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5062620>
38. Sparavigna, A. C. (2021). *The Nolan Street of Pompeii in Chapter VI of Das Templum by Heinrich Nissen (June 4, 2021)*. SSRN, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3845409> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3845409>
39. Sparavigna, A. C. (2022). *Cronologia dell'Ara Pacis Augustae, la costituzione (constitutio arae) al 4 Luglio del 13 a.C. e la dedica (dedicatio) al 30 Gennaio del 9 a.C.* Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3525870>
40. Sparavigna, A. C. (2022). *La città romana, il templum e l'archeoastronomia di Heinrich Nissen*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6997889>
41. Sparavigna, A. C. (2024). *The Town and the Templum, in the Discussions by Nissen, Nietzsche, Valeton, Catalano and many others*. *International Journal of Sciences*, 13(01), 15-45.
42. Sparavigna, A. C. (2024). *Nissen Templum in Cassirer Symbolic Forms (March 17, 2024)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4762627> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4762627>
43. Thulin, C.O. (1905). *Die Etruskische Disciplin, Parts 1–3*, Darmstadt, 1968
44. Valeton, I. M. J. (1898). *De templis Romanis*. *Mnemosyne*, 1-93.
45. Valeton, I. M. J. (1892). *De templis romanis*. *Mnemosyne*, 338-390.
46. Valeton, I. M. J. (1893). *De Templis Romanis (Continuantur ex Vol. XX pag. 390)*. *Mnemosyne*, EJ Brill.